

Dr. Chandrakant S. Ulhe¹¹Department of Physics,

Yashawantrao Chavan Arts & Science College, Mangrulpir,

SGBAU Amravati, Maharashtra, India.

chandrakantulhe2010@gmail.com

MS Received: 15.11.2024; MS Revised:28.12.2024; MS Accepted:29.12.2024)

MS 3337

(RESEARCH PAPER IN PHYSICS)

Abstract

Mn doped perovskite single phase 0.95BiFeO₃-0.5BaTiO₃ (0.95BLFO-0.5BT) multiferroic ceramic was prepared by a Sol-Gel method. XRD studies showed perovskite rhombohedral structure in space group R3c with weak traces of impurity phase in as prepared sample. SEM studies reported Mn additive act as a grain growth activator which increases grain size. The remnant polarization was found to be > 1.6 μC/cm². The considerable increased in saturation magnetization value for Mn modified 95BFO-5BT was found to be 0.3 emu/g at the applied magnetic field of 5 KOe.

Keywords: Ceramic, Sol-Gel, Dielectric, XRD, SEM

Introduction: -

Recently, dielectric properties and magnetic behavior of BFO- BT solid solution formed by solid-state reaction were reported [1-3]. But the problems associated with the high dielectric loss in solid solution of BFO-BT were not resolved and whatever the data given was depends on the authors opinion. Some of the researcher reported the high value of dielectric constant and low dielectric loss in perovskite xBaTiO₃-(1-x) BiFeO₃ ceramic [4]. However these results are still not good enough. Freshly, the researchers reported that the doping of BFO-BT by transition metals can reduce the leakage current & achieve high resistivity [5-7]. In the present work, we have reported the synthesis, structural, dielectric and magnetic properties of Mn doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT multiferroic ceramics.

Experimental: -

The Mn-doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT composite were prepared by Sol-Gel technique. The starting agent used was pure bismuth oxide, ferric nitrate, manganese nitrate and citric acid. These are dissolved in stoichiometric ratio in water. To form the complex, nitric acid was used. Ferric nitrate, manganese nitrate and bismuth nitrate solution was mixed slowly under optimized constant stirring on a magnetic stirrer at 65°C temperature. With constant stirring and avoiding formation of precipitate clear

solution was allowed to convert to a floppy gel. The powder is obtained when this gel was placed in oven at 90°C for 12 hour. in order form crystallized Mn doped BiFeO₃, the powder after crushing was placed in furnace at 600°C for 2 hours. Bismuth titanate was then added in as prepared Mn-doped BiFeO₃ in stoichiometric ratio. The complete mixture was then ball-milled 24 hours. The well mixed powder was the placed in furnace at 600°C for 04 hour in air for calcination. Finally, the pellets were prepared with polyvinyl acetate as a binding agent and sintered at 870°C for 4 hour.

Results and discussion**Phase detection and microstructure analysis of Mn doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT ceramics:-**

Figure 1 shows the XRD patterns of Mn-doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT composite. As the difficulties was arises in preparing single phase BFO because structural stability of BFO. This low structural stability of BFO was due to the volatile nature of Bismuth. [8]. As observed in BFO, BFO-BT composite, the secondary phases are also appeared in Mn doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT composite. Researchers have also reported the existence of impurity phases [9]. From the dhkl values of as prepared sample of Mn doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT, it is clear that the structure is rhombohedral with R3c space group.

Figure 1:- XRD patterns of Mn-doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT

Figure 2:- SEM of Mn doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT

Figure 2 shows microstructure surface of Mn doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT composite. It is found that the sizes of grains are non uniform. It is also observed that the grain size decreases due to the addition of Mn and sample becomes denser. This may be because the Mn ion dissolves in crystal structure which causes lattice distortion. The rapid grain growth was observe in previous studies is related to the development of oxygen vacancies which promotes the diffusion of lattice [10, 11].

3.2 Ferroelectric response of Mn doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT ceramics:-

Figure 3 shows the ferroelectric polarization hysteresis (P-E) loops measured at 100 Hz. The sample showed maximum polarization of 2.4 C/cm². The remnant polarization (Pr) is found to be 1.6 μC/cm² and coercive field (Ec) is 75 kV/cm. This is because the rhombohedral phase exhibits

Figure 3 :- Ferroelectric hysteresis (P-E) loop

Figure 4:- Magnetic hysteresis loop

a large distortion and lattice constants which develops the piezoelectric and ferroelectric [12].

Magnetic properties of Mn doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT ceramics:-

Figure 4 – shows the magnetic hysteresis loop (M-H) at room temperature for Mn doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT ceramics. The saturation magnetization 0.3 emu/gm increased due to the addition of Mn in 0.95BFO-0.5BT composite [13]. This may be due to the presence of oxygen vacancies as reported by Yu et al. [14]. Doping of Mn 2+ ions decreases the formation of Fe 2+ ion and controls the Fe 2+ /Fe 3+ charge fluctuation [15]. It is reported that the Mn doping also favors the formation of oxygen vacancies [16]. Therefore, it is clear that Mn doping

at Fe site leads to the creation of oxygen vacancies and therefore contributed in observed enhanced magnetization.

Conclusions: -

In this work, Mn doped 0.95BFO-0.5BT composite having a high insulating property is prepared by Sol-Gel method. The XRD studies confirmed the perovskite rhombohedral structure with space group R3c. SEM studies showed the dense structure of sample. The sample showed maximum polarization of 2.4 C/cm². The magnetic hysteresis (M-H) loop showed the enhanced magnetization due to the addition of Mn in 0.95BFO-0.5BT composite.

References: -

1. **M.M. Kumar, A. Srinivas, S.V. Suryanarayana, 2000** Journal of Applied Physics. 87, 855
2. **J.S. Kim, C. Chaon, C.H. Lee, P.W. 2004.** Jang, Journal of Applied Physics. 96, 468
3. **S.O. Leontsev, R.E. 2009.** Eitel, Journal of the American Ceramic Society. 92, 2957
4. **S.K. Singh, H. Ishiwara, K. Maruyama, 2006** Applied Physics Letters 88 262908
5. **D. Lin, Q. Zheng, Y. Li, Y. Wan, Q. Li and W. Zhou, 2013.** J. Euro. Ceram. Soc.33, 3023
6. **D. J. Kim et al., 2014.** J. Electrom.33, 37
7. **M. H. Lee et al, 2010** J. Korean Phys. Soc. 57, 1901
8. **Y.P. Wang, L. Zhou, M.F. Zhang, X.Y. Chen, J.M. Liu, Z.G. Liu, (2004)** Appl. Phys. Lett.84, 1731
9. **X. Zhenga, Q. Xua, Z. Wenb, X. Langa, D. Wub, T. Qiu, M.X. Xua, 2010** J. Alloys Compd. 499,108–112
10. **H.Y. Park, C.H. Nam, I.T. Seo, J.H. Choi, S. Nahm, H.G. Lee, K.J. Kim, S.M. Jeong, (2010)** J. Am. Ceram. Soc.93, 2537
11. **Y. Yan, K.H. Cho, S. Priya, (2011)** J. Am. Ceram. Soc.94, 3953
12. **H. Yang, C. Zhou, X. Liu, Q. Zhou, G. Chen, W. Li and H.Wang, (2013).** J.Euro.Ceram.Soc.33, 1177
13. **R. R. Raut, P.H. Salame, J. T. Kolte, C.S. Ulhe, P. Gopalan, 2021,** J Mater Sci: Mater Electron, DOI 10.1007/s10854-015-3810-9, ISSN: 0957-4522 (Print), ISSN- 1573-482X (Online)
14. **B. Yu, M. Li, J. Wang, Z. Hu, X. Liu, Y. Zhu, X. Zhao, 2012** Thin Solid Films520, 4089
15. **X. Qi, J. Dho, R. Tomov, M.G. Blamire, J.L.M. Driscoll, 2005** Appl. Phys. Lett.86, 062903
16. **Q. Ke, X. Lou, Y. Wang, 2010** Phys. Rev. B.82, 024102